

Yield of Ruchi in All India Coordinated trials, state trials, local verification trials, farmer's field, and maximization demonstrations.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)							
	All India Coordinated Trials				State trials ^e	LVT ^f	Farmer's field ^g	Maximization demonstration ^h
	1986 ^a	1087 ^b	1988 ^c	1989 ^d				
Ruchi	5.2	4.0	4.7	5.2	3.9	6.0	5.2	8.7
Jaya	5.3	3.8	4.4	4.7	3.3	—	—	—
Local check	4.9	3.8	4.5	4.6	3.4	5.3	4.3	—

^a Av over 13 locations. ^b Av over 12 locations ^c Av over 15 locations. ^d Av over 4 locations. ^e Av over 6 yr, 19 trials, 4 locations. ^f Av over 2 yr, 6 locations. ^g Av over 30 farmers' fields of 0.4 ha. ^h Av over 2 yr.

semitall (105 cm ± 10 cm) and, when direct seeded, can compete well with

weeds at the early vegetative phase. Grain yield averages 5-6 t/ha (see table).

Integrated germplasm improvement – upland

Evaluation of early rice genotypes for upland conditions in rolling fields of Karnataka, India

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We evaluated 25 short-duration rice genotypes (<125 d) during rainy season (May-Nov) 1987-89. The area (15°-50' N, 74°-40' E, and 697 m above sea level) has rolling fields that retain moisture for 3 to 3 1/2 mo during the normal cropping season. Annual precipitation averages about 950 mm. Total precipitation during the three cropping seasons of the experiment was 738.0, 1,034.3, and 607.3 mm,

respectively. Soil is a silty clay loam, with pH 6.3, 0.75% organic C, 9 kg P/ha, and 170 kg K/ha.

Rice was drilled in 20-cm rows at 100 kg seed/ha. The crop was fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

IET7991-11-2 and CR544-1-5 matured about 17 d earlier than high-

It matures in 130 d, is nonlodging even under high fertility because of its thick culms, and suits the rainfed lowland conditions of the state.

Ruchi grain is long, bold 35 g/1,000 grains, and suitable for puffed rice. It registered 4th in All India Coordinated trials in 1986 and first in 1989.

Ruchi may replace medium-duration, high-yielding varieties like IR8, Jaya, Pragati, and Phalguna, and has been recommended for release in 1990. ■

yielding local check Rasi (IET1444) (see table). Neela matured about 10 d earlier. These three genotypes significantly outyielded other early genotypes, and yielded as high as the local check.

In view of their earliness, IET7991-11-2 and Neela have been recommended for multilocation trials. CR544-1-5 was not considered because its grain tends to shatter when harvest is delayed. ■

Grain yield and plant characters^a of a few early rice genotypes under rainfed conditions in Mugad, Karnataka, India.

Genotype	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Duration (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)
IET7991-11-2	74.1	17.9	321.5	101	3.7
CR544-1-5	74.9	19.7	241.5	102	3.3
Neela	62.0	20.2	307.3	108	3.2
Rasi (IET1444) (local check)	79.7	18.2	250.0	118	3.1
LSD (0.05)	7.1	7.8	75.5	4.0	0.9
CV (%)	6.1	20.0	11.3	3.1	1.5

^aAv of 1987, 1988, and 1989 rainy seasons.

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fertilizer management

Impact of nursery nutrients on growth and yield of rice crop

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Nursery management is an important factor in crop production. In very thickly populated nurseries, plant roots spread

out on the soil surface and intensively exploit soil fertility. If soil fertility is low, seedlings will be thin and pale. A considerable amount of the nursery may be spoiled during pulling.

We studied the use of N and P by the rice nursery and the impact of nursery nutrition on the subsequent crop in a field experiment at Saraimiara farm. Soil of the experimental field was sandy loam,

Table 1. Effect of fertilizer applied to nursery on growth parameters of 25-d-old rice seedlings.^a

Seedling treatment	Leaves/plant (no.)	Height (cm)	100-seedling weight (g)	N content (%)	P content (%)
No N	3.8	19.2	65	1.86	0.251
100 kg N/ha	4.7	30.4	152	2.28	0.258
200 kg N/ha	5.1	31.9	243	2.34	0.312
No P	4.8	30.8	141	2.08	0.323
21.5 kg P/ha	5.0	31.3	153	2.12	0.338
43.0 kg P/ha	5.3	31.7	166	2.15	0.345
LSD (0.05)	0.3	1.01	20	0.04	0.005

^a 2 yr pooled data.

pH 7.8 with 176 kg available N, 5.13 kg P, and 164.3 kg K/ha. A bed 5 × 1 m was prepared to raise the nursery (Jaya variety). Treatments are given in the table. Farmyard manure (FYM) was applied at 15 t/ha to all treatments, to ease uprooting of seedlings. Treatments were sampled 25 d after sowing to analyze growth and N and P content.

Seedlings were transplanted in the main field with 90 kg N, 13.04 kg P, and 24.89 kg K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Seedlings responded significantly to N and P (Table 1). Height and weight of

Table 2. Effect of fertilized seedlings on grain and straw yield.

Nursery treatment	Yield (t/ha)					
	Grain			Straw		
	Year 1	Year 2	Av	Year 1	Year 2	Av
No N	2.5	2.5	2.5	4.4	4.3	4.4
100 kg N/ha	2.8	2.7	2.8	5.0	4.8	4.9
200 kg N/ha	3.1	3.1	3.1	5.5	5.4	5.4
No P	2.7	2.7	2.7	7.8	4.7	4.7
21.5 kg P/ha	2.8	2.8	2.8	5.0	4.8	4.9
43.0 kg P/ha	2.9	2.8	2.9	5.1	5.0	5.1
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2		0.3	0.3	

seedlings increased, and N and P contents increased.

Yield of grain and straw was significantly higher with N-fertilized seedlings

(Table 2). No response to P was found, possibly because of the FYM added to the nursery. ■

Crop management

Effects of number of axillary buds and main crop cutting time on ratoon crop yield

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We studied the effects on ratoon crop yield of the number of axillary buds sprouting and of different cutting times for the main crop of hybrid rice variety Shanyou 63. Planting density of the main crop was 28 hills/m² with 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha as basal fertilizer and 69 kg N/ha as topdressing 15 d after full heading, to promote bud sprouting. The crop was cut at 33 cm height at different times after main crop heading. The experimental results are shown in the table.

Number of axillary buds were significantly correlated with carbohydrate content and weight of stem and sheath, which increased as cutting time of the main crop was delayed. The correlation coefficients were $r = 0.9676$ and $r = 0.9950$.

These results show that starch content of the axillary buds was increased by the photosynthate of leaves before the main crop matured.

Cutting time of the main crop was significantly correlated with yield of the main crop and number of axillary buds sprouting, number of productive panicles, and yield of the ratoon crop. Regression equations were

Number of axillary buds and productive panicles, and yield of ratoon rice with different cutting times of the main crop. Southern Sichuan, China, 1989.

Item	Cutting time (d after main crop heading)				
	22 d	25 d	28 d	31 d	34 d
Dry weight of stem and sheath of main crop (g/hill)	12.51	12.31	12.88	13.87	16.91
Carbohydrate content of stem and sheath of main crop (%)	1.6	2.2	1.8	2.1	8.6
Maturity of main crop grain at cutting (%)	61.5	64.7	77.6	84.7	100.0
Number of axillary buds sprouting before main crop harvest (no./m ²)	0.00	0.00	0.84	3.64	27.16
Maximum number of axillary buds sprouting (no./m ²)	221.2	126.0	128.8	207.2	274.4
Productive panicles in ratoon crop (no/m ²)	187.6	123.3	126.0	187.6	257.6
Grain yield of ratoon crop (t/ha)	1.5	1.4	1.1	1.3	1.8
Grain yield of main crop (t/ha)	6.4	7.3	7.7	7.7	8.1

Grain yield of the main crop	$\hat{y} = 257.8133 + 8.4867x$
Number of axillary buds sprouting	$\hat{y} = 87.4946 - 6.1322x + 0.1135x^2$
Ratoon crop panicle number	$\hat{y} = 68.8988 - 4.83x + 0.0906x^2$
Grain yield of ratoon crop	$\hat{y} = 772.9456 - 50.8443x + 0.9274x^2$

Cutting the main crop 34 d after heading, when axillary buds began sprouting, resulted in the highest yields for both the main crop and the ratooning crop. Yield of the ratoon crop was attributed to higher numbers of productive panicles. ■

Integrated pest management – diseases

Diseases of rice in Cameroon

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Rice is a relatively new crop in Cameroon; it is currently grown on about 20,000 ha of irrigated and upland fields. Irrigated rice accounts for more than 90% of the land area under rice and contributes about 94% of annual production (Table 1). Upland rice is grown as a subsistence crop by peasant farmers in isolated areas of the country.

The Cameroonian farmer is constrained by a number of abiotic, biotic, and socioeconomic factors. Among the biotic factors, diseases pose the most problems, causing yield losses of 10-30% every year.

Development of varieties with resistance to major diseases would help stabilize rice production. We carried out disease surveys in 1988 wet season (Jul-Dec) and 1989 dry season (Jan-May) to more precisely define the rice disease situation for input to the rice improvement program.